

LINGUOCULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF IDIOMS WITH AN ANTHROPONYM COMPONENT IN LITERARY TEXT

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the problems of proper anthroponym which studies proper names in Modern English and Uzbek. It gives information about linguocultural characteristics of idioms with an anthroponym component in translations of literary text.

Key words: proper names, anthroponym, culture, translation, idiom.

In linguistics of the XXI century the position of close interaction between the culture and the language of the people who speak it becomes fundamental. The language has the ability to reflect the cultural and national mentality of its speakers, which confirms the importance of the linguistic and cultural aspect in the linguistic and cultural analysis of a literary text.

Cultural linguistics is a fairly young discipline that emerged from linguistics and cultural studies and studies language and culture in their relationship and mutual influence. It is extremely important to study culture through language, and language through culture, since it is the language material that most often becomes the source of information that is necessary for a deep understanding of a person and the world in which he lives. At the turn of the millennium, a new scientific paradigm is emerging, based on the idea of the anthropocentricity of language. Its essence lies in switching the interests of the researcher from the objects of knowledge to the subject, that is, the person in the language and the language in the person are analyzed. Over time, the idea of the anthropocentricity of language has become universally recognized and key in linguistics¹.

Now the goal of linguistic analysis can no longer be simply to identify the various characteristics of a language system. It is the idea of a person that acts as the basis for many linguistic constructions. The formation of the anthropocentric paradigm prompted scientists to turn linguistic problems towards a person and his place in culture, since the focus of culture and cultural tradition is a linguistic

personality in all its diversity. A literary text is a multidimensional, complex phenomenon, which includes many aspects that characterize its main properties. It is precisely because of their complexity and multidimensionality that literary texts become an excellent material for all kinds of linguistic research. They open up incredible opportunities for scientists for linguistic and cultural analysis, because any work of art is created by the author and perceived by the reader in the context of the relationship of culture, thinking and language. Proper names is a word or ground of words recognized as indicating or tending to indicate the object or objects to which it refers by virtue of its distinctive sound alone, without regard to any meaning possessed by that sound alone, without the start or acquired by it through association with said object or objects.

One of the two largest classes of proper names is that which provides designation for places for continents countries, provinces, towns, villages and even private residences, not to speak of expanses of water, mountains, promontories, and so forth. In this class all the four conditions mentioned above come into play, but with different deserving if comment. There are but few localities in the world so different from the rest that they eschew proper names and are habitually represented by brief descriptions; indeed can instance only the similarity of the entities named there is not that degree which exists between the stars as seen by a terrestrial observer, but it would be a grievous misrepresentation of my point if someone objected that the Mediterranean and London have nothing in common except that both are localities. When the sea is compared with sea and town with town the difficulty of selecting features characteristic enough to serve as the basis for differentiating descriptions will be appreciated to the full. The fact that places change from century is another reason for giving them immutable names of their own to emphasize their continuity, though this case of proper names exercises less influence in place names than it does in names of persons. The interest without which no place would be given a name does not spring from exactly the same kind of source as the interest that prompted the naming of the stars. There the needs of mariners and of these concerned with the measurement of time have co-operated with the scientific preoccupation of a small beady of specialists. As regards places, there is scarcely anyone without a home or haunt of his own which is a vital distance places varies greatly and in the majority of cases is simply non-existent.

Anthroponym determines a certain personality from the great quantity of people. This statement is very deep because it takes lots of peculiarities of the

determined subjects and also the speaker's attitude to the surrounding world. The origin history of the proper names is closely connected with culture and ideology of society where they are used. This aspect interprets the fact that anthroponyms are frequently used in proverbs and in fiction texts. So, the problem of the article lies in the great functional potential of anthroponyms. Anthroponyms have the function of the connection between a man and his surrounding world or society in common. Every personality lives among people who have their own names. Every such a name creates a certain continuum or certain national and cultural area that is common for all the language collective but it is individual for every its representative. Studying anthroponymy systems of different European countries we may notice the same out features that include the same elements, namely it is the presence of a proper name and a surname. But there are lots of differences in other cases because every anthroponymy system is the unique phenomenon in all ontological aspects of determining of anthroponyms.

For example, the anthroponymy model in the Ukrainian language consists of a name and patronymic. The English model consists of three components that include a first name, second name and surname. The German anthroponymy model consists of two components, they are name and surname that may be multi component. Anthroponym is the device of person's identification as the special form of communication. In different spheres of life (at work, in the family, in the rest time) the parallel models of names are used. They are determined by national and cultural features of the communicational behavior, the person's preference to a certain referent group and also the by a social role. Anthroponyms play a big role in the studying of culture and history of a certain country. In the ground of the anthroponymy lies the literature onomastics that has become very popular last years because modern science about the language has the anthropocentric direction. Anthroponyms used in fiction texts serve as the object of learning of poetical and literary onomastics. The studying of literary onomastics has begun not long ago. Magazanyk Y. has noticed that it is hard to imagine the proper name that priori plays a great literary and esthetic role because its role in the language is quiet poor². The functions of names in the society are determined by social needs. It means that all the functions of proper names are social because they are realized only in social and speech situations. According to Superanskaya A. social legalization of personality is one of the main

²Магазаник Э.Б. Ономапозтика или «Поворящие» имена в литературе / Э.Б. Магазаник. – Т.: Фан, 1978. – 146 с.

functions of anthroponyms³. Proper names serve likely as the national symbols, namely they realize the function of the ethnic symbol that point the belonging of native speakers to a certain ethnic group. Many researchers point out the informative function of anthroponyms. The fiction prose doesn't reflect the real conditions of life but it copies different social phenomena including the use of anthroponyms. Proper name belongs to one of the main elements in the process of creating the images in fiction texts. The difference between the proper names of real communication and those of a fiction text lies in the fact that the proper names of a fiction text are created for the concrete hero taking into account his character, social state etc. So, the proper names in the fiction text play as well as the function of identification as the function of creation of the fiction image of a certain hero.

For this reason, most places are for him –mere names. Again, it accords well with Mill's view of the meaningless of proper names that place names can prove serviceable with only a minimum of knowledge. When a railway – journey is being planned one does not stop to inquire details about the junctions at which one has to change, nor is more information required in giving an address than to specify the larger and smaller regions within which the particular place is located. The interest that different persons display in a given place is apt to be extremely heterogeneous and the virtue of a proper name is that, since it embraces the whole of its object, it caters to all requirements without bias in any direction. It is superfluous to waste words over the utility of place-names in locating other places than those designated by them; the postman and the pedestrian are here the best witnesses⁴.

Phraseology has been one of the interesting and problematic topics among linguists. The notion of phraseology was first put forward by a Swiss scientist Charles Bally in his work "Stylistique française" (French stylistics) (Bally, 1909). Phraseology is a small branch of linguistics which deals with the phraseological units of language, a linguistic unit consisting of a combination of more than one independent lexeme form and having a figurative spiritual nature. Its meaning cannot be deduced from the meaning of its components and they do not allow their lexical components to be changed or substituted. There has been given a classification of phraseological units and has arisen a problematic issue as to the classification of phraseology from the different viewpoints among linguists⁵.

³ Суперанская А.В. общая теория имени собственного / А.В. Суперанская – М. Наука 1973 – 367 стр

⁴ Alan Gardener The theory of proper names. P 126

⁵ Суперанская А.В. общая теория имени собственного / А.В. Суперанская – М. Наука 1973 – 367 стр

Therefore, according to a particular point of view they have been classified into a number of subgroups, such as A. V. Koonin classified phraseological units on the basis of functions of them in speech, V. V. Vinogradov has given his own classification on consideration of their motivation, N. Amosova categorized phraseological units into two subgroups, idioms and phrasemes, depending on whether just one component or both are used in phraseological- bound meaning, A. I. Smirnitsky suggested a classification of phraseological units on the basis of their semantic and grammatical inseparability and he worked out a structural classification of phraseological units, comparing them with a word. However, the most interesting classification of phraseological units is the classification with onomastic component, and they are, in turn, categorized into a number of subgroups, such as those with anthroponyms, toponyms, ethonyms, zoonyms, astronoms, cosmonyms, chrononyms, phaleronyms, georthonyms, documentonyms, ergonyms, ideonyms, chrematonyms and biblionyms (Radjabova, 2021).

Recently, the researches have aimed at the study of phraseological units as transmitters of cultural information and embodiments of cultural values (Ashurova & Galiyeva, 2019). The reason behind this aim is the fact that as one of the basic ways of linguistic representation of linguoculturology can be regarded phraseological units (Telia, 1996). Another indispensable function of phraseological units in imparting cultural information is the fact that they denote a fully or partially figurative meaning (Kunin, 1970) or they carry connotations and have an emphatic or intensifying function in a text (Glaser, 1998). Krasnix also claims that phraseological unit is often carriers of cultural connotation as a result of research on the study of Slovene phraseology for the culture- specific interpretation (Krasnix, 2008). It is evident that the indispensable connection between phraseology and culture lies in the fact that onomastic components of phraseological units reveal cultural identity of a certain nation.

According to Dobrovolsky and Pirainen, speakers perceive phraseological units with a proper name typical of a given national culture as being culturally connoted (Dobrovolsky & Pirainen, 2005). It means that a phraseological unit used in discourse must be understood by the receiver and this process of comprehension is influenced by linguistic, social and cultural factors (Szerszunowicz, 2008). That is why phraseological unit is deeply national and gives opportunity to understand nation's history and character (Rasulova, 2008). Moreover, phraseological units with anthroponomic components are

very often culture- specific because they carry a unique historical, national phenomena belonging to only one nation. Phraseological units containing anthroponymic constituents compose one of the most intriguing and fascinating subsystems in every language and culture. It is defined as the reflection of the anthroponymic character of phraseology and language in general.

The majority of the anthroponymic phraseological units have a rich cultural background, conceptualized in national memory as rigid associations-personalities (Abdusamatov, 2021). Such units as a universal phenomenon are one of the most interesting objects for the contrastive investigations in, especially, two separate English and Uzbek languages. Furthermore, according to Solntzev, phraseological units with anthroponomical component in modern English constitute a larger group of over 1000 units, which predetermines the need for studying the mechanism of qualitative transformation of anthroponomy as a part of phraseological unit (Solntzev, 1977). As Ergashova claims anthroponomical component phraseological unit in English include over 40 units as compared to Uzbek where such units are just a few and still insufficiently investigated (Ergasheva, 2011). This is another issue which has to be investigated since establishing a comparative study on English and Uzbek anthroponomical component phraseological units reveals multiple peculiarities in both nations. Having investigated the anthroponomy of both English and Uzbek languages and their role as a phraseological component, Isayev came to conclusion that such phraseological units in English came mainly from religion, political figures and literary texts, whereas those in Uzbek came from proverbs, religion, mythological and historical sources, indicating that such examples are just a few (Isayev, 2015).

As a result of her research on this issue, Ergasheva hold the view that in English the majority of such phraseological units appeared as a result of the process of communication, whereas in Uzbek such phraseological units are not much (Ergasheva, 2011). This proves the fact that there will be a huge discrepancy in both languages as to the analysis of such phraseological units since there will not be an equivalence of meaning and structure between English and Uzbek anthroponomical component phraseology. The outcome of research conducted by Bally revealed that European languages have drawn vivid and expressive images from the treasury of biblical and ancient myths (Bally, 1955). As is the case with Turkish languages, including Uzbek, in whose stock there is an abundance of expressive images deriving from Koran and folklore (Azizova, 2018). Moreover, Teshaboyeva Z. Q. is of the same opinion with Azizova F. S. that

they are mainly used in literary texts to embellish images and enrich the language stock (Teshaboyeva, 2021). They are represented in the language, doubtlessly, by means of phraseological units. Another finding which was revealed by Radjabova M. A. is that one of the most common onomastic units in world linguistics are anthroponyms and toponyms, each of which is, in turn, divided into several subtypes (Radjabova, 2021). Phraseological units with such components found in English and Uzbek languages indicated that the majority of English phraseological units with anthroponym components correspond to mainly Uzbek proverbs with anthroponyms from the viewpoint of their meaning. According to contrastive exploration of phraseological units with anthroponym components conducted by Abdusamadov Z. N., such phraseological units reveal one of the deepest layers of the picture of the world introducing universal and specific features of a native speaker and his culture and they contribute to the preservation of the collective cultural identity (Abdusamadov, 2021). He also holds the view that names as the element of culture participate in the linguistic fields, such as phraseological units that include phrases, proverbs and sayings, etc.

As a result of the research conducted by Ismailova Z. I. L, the national specificity of a language lies in the onomastic components of phraseological units, which included geographical names, historical phrases, names of plants and names of clothes (Azizova, 2018). Besides, Azizova F. S. claims that the national- cultural peculiarities of phraseological unit come from extralinguistic factors, including social, economical, cultural conditions as the consequence of her research on names of streets, names of clothes and names of political figures as the components of phraseological units (Azizova, 2018). Taking everything into consideration, phraseology as a complex area of the linguistic system is a developing field of research and has attracted interest from many aspects. Phraseology itself covers a wide range of unexplored areas, such as the national-cultural specificity of the components, mainly onomastic ones, of phraseological units and the integral connection between phraseology and linguoculturology. Another aspect of the research article which was not investigated is that the structural and semantic analysis of the anthroponomic component phraseological units of English and Uzbek languages has not been comprehensively revealed yet. The objectives of the article can be regarded as crucial because the establishment of the differences and similarities of such kind of phraseological units in both languages enrich national and cultural heritage and their role as a representation of national realia adorns speech and texts.

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